

Short Report

Tuberculosis of the Breast

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Tuberculosis of the breast is a rare disease that is usually manifested by a breast lump or an abscess. The aim of this report is to remind physicians that this condition still exists, although it is extremely rare.

A 55-year-old housewife was admitted with a three-month history of a painful mass in the right breast. She had had a history of the presence of a palpable but not painful right axillary gland for 30 years. Physical examination revealed an enlarged right axillary lymph node and nodular lesions in the right breast with associated skin erythema without nipple discharge. The rest of the physical examination was unremarkable. Erythrocyte sedimentation rate was 40 mm/h and the rest of the routine laboratory data were within normal limits. The tuberculin skin test with 5 TU showed 15 mm induration, without history of previous BCG administration. A chest radiography revealed clear lung fields. Mammogram of the right breast (Figure 1) showed multiple nodular lesions. Histological examination of the excised right axillary lymph node and an incisional biopsy specimen of the breast showed granulomatous inflammation with caseous necrosis and Langhans' giant cells. Treatment was commenced with daily isoniazid, rifampicin, and pyrazinamide. After one month, the patient appeared to have improved clinically and a repeat mammogram (Figure 2) showed that nodular lesions had almost completely disappeared.

Most of the cases reported in the literature occurred in patients 20 to 40 years of age (1,2). Mammography tuberculosis is said to be more common during pregnancy and the puerperium, in association with active pulmonary tuberculosis (3,4). Although the extrapulmonary presentation of tuberculosis is more common in the elderly than in younger patients, mammary tuberculosis is rare in older women (5,6). Primary disease is assumed to exist when no other focus of tuberculosis is demonstrated. In our patient there was the evidence of previous tuberculosis with axillary lymphadenopathy, but no evidence of cavitation or active disease in the lungs. Domingo et al. have reported a case of mammary tuberculosis in whom a relationship between enlarged axillary glands and the breast was disclosed by inoculation of contrast (6). The disease in our patient was of the multinodular type. The clinical diagnosis of mammary tuberculosis is difficult and more complicated when carcinoma and tuberculosis of the breast occur together (7). Ideally diagnosis should be made by histologic findings and culture, but, so far, the bacillus could be isolated in only 25 to 35 percent of the reported cases (4).

Tuberculosis of the breast is rare but still occurs. It should be considered as a possible diagnosis not only in younger and childbearing-age women but also in elderly patients with or without evidence of tuberculosis elsewhere.

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Figure 1. Right mammogram obtained on admission. Multiple tuberculous nodules are seen.

Figure 2.

Right mammogram obtained one month after chemotherapy. Note disappearance of nodules. Arrows show the site of incisional biopsy cicatrix.

